

Effect of Electronic Banking on the Economic Growth of Nigeria [2009-2018]

***¹Njoku, Charles Odinakachi, ²Nwadike, Emmanuel Chijioke & ³Azuama, Godwin Uchenna,**

^{1,2,3}Department of Financial Management Technology, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT: This study examines the impact of electronic banking on economic growth in Nigeria over the period of 2009 - 2018 using quarterly data. Secondary data were collected from the CBN statistical Bulletin and the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics so as to establish the relationship between the dependent variable (Real GDP) and the independent variables (Automated Teller Machines, Point-of-Sale, Internet Banking and Mobile Banking). The research adopted the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and the results of the analysis show that electronic banking has significantly impacted on the economic growth of Nigeria. The VECM result shows that R^2 is 0.5897, which shows that the model explains about 58.97% of the total variations in Economic growth as explained by the independent variables during the period of the study, while 41.03% is explained by variables not included in the model. The result of the analysis shows that Electronic Banking has a significant relationship with Nigeria's economic growth, while Point of Sales, Internet Banking and Mobile Banking, individually have no significant effect on Nigeria's economic growth, while Automated Teller Machine has significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria for the period under consideration. The research recommends that the government should reduce the charges on the use of electronic means of transactions so as to encourage people to use them more often.

Keywords: Electronic Banking, Economic Growth, Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, Point-of-Sale, Automated Teller Machine

I. INTRODUCTION

Banking operations were manually done before the emergence of electronic banking, this resulted to slowdown in financial transactions. This manual system involves humans recording transactions on ledgers. Most times counting of money which should be done through computers or electronic machine were computed and counted manually which is not a very accurate method and therefore prone to human errors.

Babatunde and Ogbeide (2017), Electronic banking is an online banking system that gives everybody the opportunity to easily access banking activities without stepping into the banking hall, thus promoting financial inclusion. He stated that the banking activities may include retrieving an account balance, making electronic money transfers and retrieving an account history electronically.

Electronic banking is the use of computers and telecommunications to enable banking transactions to be done by computers or telephones instead of through human interaction. (Okoro, 2014) He further explained that before the early 1980s, electronic banking really took off with the arrival of the world- wide-web (WWW) when traditional banks offered their clients account access online while some new banks started.

Electronic banking can be seen as an umbrella term for the process by which a customer may perform banking transactions electronically without visiting a brick and mortar institution. (Sameni, 2012)

Clive (2007), in his Academic dictionary of banking, explained electronic banking to be a form of banking in which funds are exchanged between banks or financial institutions via electronic signals, rather than an exchange of physical cash or other negotiable instruments. Omotayo, G. (2007, p.3) explained electronic banking as a banking method in which funds are transferred from one account to another using computerized online systems.

Edet (2008), defined electronic banking as a banking transaction method in which transactions are resolved electronically with the use of electronic gadgets such as ATMs, POS terminals, GSM phones, and V-cards e.t.c. handled by e-holders, bank customers, and stake holders.

Electronic banking can come in different forms. The use of Point of Sale (POS), internet banking, Automated Teller Machines and Mobile banking are different forms of electronic banking.

A POS transaction refers to what happens when a product or service is purchased by a customer from a merchant, using a point of sale machine. A POS system is similar to a POS terminal. Nevertheless, a POS terminal refers to the electronic equipment that processes the credit/debit card payments. The POS software coupled with the computer terminal is used by most businesses to manage operations and transactions. (Okoro, 2014)

Okoro, (2014) defines internet Banking (Online banking) as an electronic payment system that enables customers of a bank or other financial institution to conduct a range of financial transactions through the financial institution's website. Internet banking gives one the ability to manage his/her money online with a mobile device or computer. The stress of visiting a bank to carry out a transaction is greatly or completely eradicated.

An Automated Teller Machine (ATM) is an electronic telecommunications device that enables customers of financial institutions to perform financial transactions, such as cash withdrawals, deposits, transfer funds, or obtaining account information, at any time and without the need for direct interaction with bank staff (Okoro, 2014). The machines are accessed through bank designated electronic cards.

Mobile banking is a form of electronic banking service provided by a bank or other financial institutions that allow its customers to carry out financial transactions from anywhere in the world using their mobile phones. This is done through the use of mobile Apps created by the banks.

Economic growth is an increase in the amount of economic goods and services produced in a country within a specified period of time. It stated that it can be measured in nominal or real (adjusted for inflation) terms. And that traditionally, aggregate economic growth is measured in terms of gross national product (GNP) or gross domestic product (GDP).

Britannica (2019) defines it as the process by which a nation's wealth increases over time.

Unlike other countries of the World, Nigeria did not welcome the idea of electronic banking early. Societe Generale Bank of Nigeria (SGBN), in 1986 initiated online, real-time banking in its 5 branches in Lagos Metropolis. However, most Nigerian banks did not adopt e-banking until the early 2000s. Today, the most used electronic payment systems in Nigeria are ATM, IB, MB, and POS. Recently e-banking has been seen as the powerful energy influencing the landscape of the banking sector fundamentally, in particular, towards a more competitive industry. E-banking has bridged the gap between different financial institutions, enabled new products and services in the financial industry and made the existing ones available in different packages. (Agbala, 2008).

The flexibility, speed, accessibility and convenience of Electronic Banking has made it really popular and widely embraced by the masses. It enables users to easily make transfer of funds, make purchases (both online and offline), and also pay bills; faster and at a lower cost.

This study aims at carefully evaluating the effect of electronic banking on the economic growth of Nigeria.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Electronic banking should be a system by which at least 80% of all banking transactions are carried out without stepping a foot into the banking hall. This means that a perfect internet and mobile banking system is there to satisfy the need of all internet and mobile banking users. The ATM and POS systems should be readily available to satisfy all deposit and withdrawal needs. But this happens only in an ideal World. This would enhance the role of banks as financial intermediaries. The intermediation efficiency entails financial intermediaries being able to harmonise the transfer of funds from the surplus spending units to the deficit spending units and vice versa.

The Nigerian banking system is not completely efficient yet, as there are lapses evident in the day to day running of electronic banking by Nigerian banks today. These lapse ranges from delayed transaction process time, delayed remittance time in case there was a failed transaction. Most times it takes the bank 20 working days or more to track a failed transaction on a Point-of-Sale system. This leaves the customers in fear, as most Nigerians are poor and can't afford to have their money pending while the banks conducts their rigorous search on the transaction.

Another major problem is in the low rate of adoption by the citizens of the country. The government introduced a policy termed "Cashless Policy" in the year 2012. Even as there are different ways of withdrawing money electronically; people still flood the banking halls to manually withdraw their money on a daily basis.

One of the major reasons Nigeria adopted a cashless policy, which gave rise to electronic banking was to combat corruption in the country. But that didn't stop corruption. Instead it upgraded their means of operation. These days, with just a snap of a finger on a tablet or computer, one can easily empty the account of another without having to carry any physical cash. Some decades back, robbers take Ghana must go bags to banks or people's houses to rob them of their

physical cash. These days' robbers go to people with POS systems and have them insert their debit cards to have their accounts emptied. Banks have had moments when their systems were hacked into, and millions of money electronically embezzled in a space of some minutes or hours.

These are problems that this study is going to look at and devise means of solving in the nearest future.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

It is important to look at the works of researchers who have studied the impact of electronic banking on a country's economic growth. Here are a few;

Isibor, Omankhanlen, Okoye, Achugamonu, Adebayo, Afolabi and Ayodeji (2018) studied the impact of electronic banking on both customers' satisfaction and economic growth. The methodology employed for testing the hypotheses is a statistical parametric test called Pair Sample t-test through the use of SPSS statistical package. The study rejects both null hypotheses which mean that e-banking has improved both customers' satisfaction and caused economic growth in Nigeria. The study recommends adequate legislation on all aspects of e-banking so that both the operators of the system and the public can be adequately protected. Also, it recommended that banks should charge low or no fees for e-banking services in order to motivate their customers to take advantage of e-banking services.

Babatunde and Salawudeen (2017) examined the impact of electronic banking in the Nigerian banking industry and financial institutions. Both primary and secondary data was employed in the study which had Access bank as its case study. The study concluded that electronic banking has enhanced the bank's efficiency, making it more productive and effective.

Ogbeide, Nwamaka and Ishiwu (2016) investigated the impact of electronic banking on Nigerian economic growth. They made emphasis on the long-debate that has been made on the relationship between financial development and the growth of the economy. They discussed that the banking sub-sector of the financial sector is an important part of the sector because of it linking of the deficit and surplus areas of the economy. Electronic banking (E-banking) is now one of the most important and modern development and applications that has been witnessed in the banking sector for the last years. It further determined if there exists a long-run relationship between e-banking and economic growth in Nigeria employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bond testing technique. Economic growth (RGDP) was regressed on some measures of e-banking (Automated Teller machine, Mobile banking, Web banking and Point on Sales Terminal) for the period 2009 to 2014 quarterly data. The Pairwise Granger Causality test was also adopted to determine the direction of causality. The results of the study showed that e-banking had significant impact on economic growth. ATMs and MB were found to have a positive impact on economic growth while POS and WB showed a negative impact. A one unit increase in the use of ATM and MB leads to 4.2489 and 19.8707 increases in RGDP respectively while one naira increase in POS and WB leads to 15.262 and 53.757 naira fall in RGDP. The result of the study further showed that there is a long-run relationship between e-banking and economic growth and that e-banking Granger causes economic growth in Nigeria. The study thus recommended the improvement of the technological base of the country and policy measures to encourage the efficient performance of the banking sector as well as a regulation and control of the banking activities. Okifo and Igbunu (2015) evaluated the adoption of e-payment system in Nigeria, looking at its economic benefits and challenges. The lives of many people has undeniably been made better by technology. Technology has had big impacts on distance, space and even time. The invention of electronic payment systems was one of the greatest technological innovations in banking, finance and commerce. Electronic payments gives people the opportunity to operate from any location at any point in time without visiting conventional offices to pay bills, taxes, fines, or even purchase licenses. The ease of use, cost, security, authorization, acceptability, industry or even the preferences of consumers largely determines the success of e-payment systems. Despite all the benefits that e-payment systems brings to the nation, banks and individuals, it still has its challenges that it came with. The challenges can be categorized into security, infrastructures, legal and regulatory issues as well as socio-cultural issues.

Musa, Kurfi, and Hassan (2015) looked at the impact of online banking on the performance of the Nigerian banking sector argued that majority of the business sectors, including banks, have taken advantage of using IT to enhance their business operations. The use of IT has led Nigerian banks to e-banking, and this e-banking has revolutionised the entire banking industry by scaling borders and bringing about new opportunities. Nowadays, most of the banks have website on the Internet in order to extend their services globally to provide executive services, attain their customers 24/7, and promote quality of service delivery. To achieve the research objective, the data of this study was gathered by analysing the financial statement of the 21 commercial banks in Nigeria where information, such as ROA, ROE, and NIM, were gathered.

Okoro (2014) examined the impact selected e-payment instruments on the intermediation efficiency of the Nigerian economy between 2006 and 2011. These findings were made by him: that there's a significant relationship between ATM, POS, internet services values and the intermediation efficiency of the Nigerian economy. However, the study also

revealed that there is no significant relationship between mobile service value and intermediation efficiency of the Nigerian economy within the number of years under study. The findings implied that the main instruments employed by the customers of the deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria are ATM, POS and internet services (internet banking), which could be as a result the level of campaigns or awareness created by the Nigerian banks. On the contrary, the insignificant impact of the mobile service values to the intermediation efficiency could also be as a result of the user's ignorance or the banks' inability to effectively market the product. In addition to that, the result shows that the intermediation efficiency of the Nigerian economy gets better as the usage of the selected e-payment instruments increases. Hence this study recommends that the banks should up their game in marketing these products in Nigeria.

Obademi and Adegboyega (2014) examined the relationship between banking development and economic growth and the direction of the causality in Nigeria emphasizing on the financial repression hypothesis over the period 1970-2010. They employed the ordinary least square method of regression analysis and the Pairwise Granger Causality test. The results of the study showed that banks have significant positive impacts on growth in Nigeria under all the regulatory regimes than the deregulation period. It was however concluded that although banking development showed positive impacts on growth, it cannot be said to be the propelling force for economic growth in Nigeria.

Okoro and Kigho (2013) while researching on the problems and prospects of E-transaction in Nigeria revealed through their study that there is a significant relationship between e-transaction and economic growth. They stated that as at the time of their study, e-transaction was still at its infant stage and therefore, needs the trust and support of the government, corporate bodies, and individuals to be a successful innovation in the country.

Madueme (2010) studied the impact of information communication technology on banking efficiency. She discovered in her study, which was carried out across 13 banks, that information technology improved the efficiency of those banks after its adoption. Therefore she made the recommendations below: banks should increase their investment on ICT, that banks should also diversify software packages for better operational efficiency supply, more favourable importation policies should be made and local industries that are into the acquisition, production and assembly of information technology materials should be encouraged by the government to enable them achieve optimal performance and greater information utilization.

For studies done in other countries of the world, Petkovski and Kjosevski (2014) carried out a study on the an empirical analysis on the question if banking sector development promote economic growth using 16 countries in Central and South Eastern Europe. They employed a Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) dynamic panel method in the analysis. The result showed that credit to the private sector and interest margin (IM) used as measure of bank development negatively affected economic growth, while RQM was positively related to economic growth.

Maiyo (2013) examined the effect of electronic banking on financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study showed that commissions and fees from credit cards, debit cards and mobile banking has a significant impact on returns on asset whereas fees and commission from online banking as well as the amount of money that commercial banks invest in electronic banking to install, train staff and maintain the platforms has little or no effect on return on assets. The performance of deposit money banks has been enhanced greatly by the adoption of e-banking , due to increased efficiency, effectiveness and productivity. The study suggest that commercial banks should strategically expand their electronic services for the long-run, in order to achieve customer satisfaction and increase their profitability.

Erhan and Sudi (2013) gave an overview of GDP and internet banking relations in the European Union versus China. This is their point of view:

The internet diffused rapidly throughout the economy of the world after 1995. A robust banking sector is vital to each country to prompt economic growth and maintain financial stability for the entire economic system. Hence the outburst of information and technology encouraged banks to invest more on technology to optimise return and attract more customers who will not welcome less below-average services. The EU has long sought to make a single financial area where consumers in one country can benefit from banking activities in other countries. The development of the internet as a platform for the provision of e-banking services, the creation of a pan European market for banking services became realistic. Moreover, despite the long term profitability challenges, most top banks in EU have spent and are still spending in providing internet banking services as a new cost effective delivery channel, driven by cost reduction, increase in market share and retention of customers. Therefore, the Chinese banking system which has benefited from the strong government protection against foreign competitors is not generally well understood. Even though internet banking in China has witnessed a rapid growth in the past few years, it is still believed to be in its early development stage when compared to other developed nations. Finally, good economic conditions have a positive influence on banking sector performance. The bank should enjoy conditions related to economic boom as much as possible to cushion the negative effects which it may face during the economic recession. It is in this view that his paper discusses how the internet is creating new applications for banking services.

Hassan, Mukhtar, Ullah, Shafique, and Rehman (2012) used the data of retail payments for all 27 EU member states from 1995 to 2009 to demonstrate technological advancements in payment systems has been productive in terms of bank operating costs and revenue increase. The result of their study did show that migration to efficient e-payment systems has a positive impact on GDP, consumption and trade, and that this relationship is the best for card payments.

Raja et al. (2008) investigated the impact of e-payment system on business opportunities. They figured out that because of the growth of internet users, several electronic mechanisms had been developed to see to the diversity of applicants. The researchers categorized the e-payments into three major groups, viz, cash like systems, cheque like systems, and hybrid systems which were further classified into credit cards, debit cards, and e-cheques. They figured out 3 main electronic payment related issues, which they categorized as security issues, low interest among businessmen, and heavy reliance on the conventional payment methods. They also explained that there were technical and cultural problems which distort the path of e-payments. However, to make e-payments more effective security threats like cybercrimes should be greatly reduced, and people should be made to understand that conventional payment methods are more time consuming than the e-payment methods. They should also be educated on the benefits of using card payment systems instead of carrying cash and cheques around.

Jain and Hundal (2006) analysed the importance of mobile banking and barriers within its adoption. The paper studied the forces that can pose as hiccups in the adoption of the mobile banking service. The actual target of the study was to seek out the explanations or reasons why people were yet to fully accept the technology despite the fact that it provided much advantage to the banking customers as compared to the old technologies used. The paper tried to point out the various barriers, namely access problems, dissatisfaction and inability of service providers in the adoption of mobile banking services. The results of the study showed that the users got disheartened by the complicated function while accessing the mobile banking services which caused their dissatisfaction level to rise, as no proper guidance was provided to them. Jain and Hundal suggested that service providers should be aware of their customers' issues. The findings of the study gave a quick outlook for the practical implication for managers and policy-makers who need to draft out strategies and make decisions so as to cater the unexplored services market.

Paul (2006) discussed the role of technology and scope of remote channels, their implication, strength, weakness, opportunities and threats in banking sector. Paul posited that information technology influences banking in two ways. Firstly, it had led to the reduction of costs inherent in the management of information by replacing the traditional methods with automated processes. Secondly, it had transformed the ways in which customers accessed banks' products and services. The author discovered that the introduction of RTGS, NDS, and CFMS had increased the safety, security, efficiency and soundness in payment systems. Lastly, the author showed that technology had a significant impact on the structure of banking industry in the form of bank branches, bank personnel and alliance. Raghvan (2006) highlighted the changes in the banking sector due to the effect of information technology, telecommunication and electronic data processing. He also tried to visualize the perception of banks in India in the year 2020 taking into account the impact of internet banking, ATMs, EFT on the performance of banks and initiative taken in liberalization, privatization and globalization. He also examined the future of online and internet banking. Due to the proven benefits, automation of manual processes, online and internet banking was slated to increase manifold. He also examined that an estimated 46lakh net users were online as at then and in that research it was estimated to reach 160lakh by March 2008. In addition, he studied the projected indicators of banks in India in 2020 emphasizing on internet banking and electronic banking.

Krishnamurthy & Wills (2006) pointed out the benefits, risks, innovations and convenience involved in e-banking. ATM, telephones, internet banking assisted the banks to deliver the products effectively. Krishnamurthy, in his paper, also explained the operational efficiency of e-banking, which included basic e-banking, simple or advanced transactional e-banking. Each site offered a different kind of services to customers. The researcher also discussed about some risks such as loss of secrecy of the customers, financial instability, fraud prone possibilities, eruption of legal claims etc. So, the researcher recommended that banks should adopt a strategy in which risks and innovation in banking products move parallel and simultaneously.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

DATA PRESENTATION:

Table 1 presents the data for Automated Teller Machines (ATM), Point-of-Sale (POS), Mobile Banking (MB), Internet Banking (IB) and Economic Growth (GDP) from 2009Q1 to 2018Q4.

Table 1: Table of RGDP, ATM, POS, IB and MB.

YEAR	LogRGDP	LogATM	LogPOS	LogIB	LogMB
2009Q1	3.745966	2.138997	0.545307	0.641474	-1.22185
2009Q2	3.776504	2.163072	0.439333	0.715167	-0.95861
2009Q3	3.827255	2.100784	0.394452	1.718253	-0.284
2009Q4	3.843178	2.143608	0.359835	1.3485	-0.23657
2010Q1	4.106883	1.796505	0.44248	0.52763	-0.06048
2010Q2	4.118645	1.906981	0.426511	0.62941	0.136721
2010Q3	4.161865	2.06032	0.447158	0.997386	0.264818
2010Q4	4.176695	2.150756	0.651278	0.873902	0.409933
2011Q1	4.166907	2.523109	0.79796	1.382557	0.521138
2011Q2	4.182694	2.5619	0.80956	1.34262	0.570543
2011Q3	4.21402	2.588249	0.936514	0.803457	0.699838
2011Q4	4.241261	2.67768	0.984527	0.85187	0.840733
2012Q1	4.222068	2.657811	0.271842	0.804139	0.033424
2012Q2	4.254507	2.684163	0.941511	0.840733	0.692847
2012Q3	4.272661	2.698718	1.168792	0.877371	0.860937
2012Q4	4.283774	2.737916	1.355068	1.030195	1.261025
2013Q1	4.267692	2.786219	1.419625	1.05576	1.359456
2013Q2	4.304268	2.829362	1.49052	0.971276	1.461198
2013Q3	4.31605	2.862865	1.63488	1.089552	1.530456
2013Q4	4.335142	2.910283	1.782831	1.154728	1.756484
2014Q1	4.309245	2.894344	1.829046	1.220108	1.821841
2014Q2	4.341582	2.930623	1.846646	1.150449	1.87017
2014Q3	4.366102	3.011959	1.892095	1.27738	1.936966
2014Q4	4.390314	3.006701	1.983807	1.386856	2.077295
2015Q1	4.209617	2.972184	1.983671	1.357172	1.96199
2015Q2	4.220711	2.983369	2.019407	1.231724	2.001907
2015Q3	4.260274	3.004957	2.050844	1.350054	2.03866
2015Q4	4.272894	3.024642	2.130977	1.468052	2.149219
2016Q1	4.350935	3.02938	2.160619	1.500922	2.131105
2016Q2	4.375431	3.054801	2.214075	1.41946	2.226033
2016Q3	4.429284	3.095797	2.278639	1.487986	2.348422
2016Q4	4.470288	3.186631	2.415941	1.639785	2.362313
2017Q1	4.418779	3.176684	2.456336	1.668106	2.415958
2017Q2	4.435628	3.188712	2.510719	1.569257	2.470175
2017Q3	4.473575	3.192779	2.561757	1.658774	2.379052
2017Q4	4.500346	3.263056	2.638639	1.743118	2.486884
2018Q1	4.457624	3.195609	2.676447	1.783475	2.517354
2018Q2	4.490735	3.20498	2.735303	1.726401	2.613387
2018Q3	4.528673	3.201673	2.813187	1.839289	2.697299
2018Q4	4.552274	3.23476	2.853911	2.345433	2.773011

Source: CBN statistical bulletin (2018) and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)

V. RESULT PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

Table 4.1 above shows the values of Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Automated Teller Machines (ATM), Point-of-Sale (POS), Internet Banking (IB) and Mobile Banking (MB) of Nigeria for the period of 2009 to 2018. The relationship can be stated as shown below:

$$RGDP = b_0 + b_1ATM_t + b_2POS_t + b_3IB_t + b_4MB_t + U_t$$

Where:

RGDP= Real Gross Domestic Product (dependent variable).

ATM = Automated Teller Machines

POS = Point-of-Sale

IB = Internet Banking

MB = Mobile Banking

b₀= Intercept.

b₁, b₂, b₃, b₄ = Parameters to be estimated.

VI. UNIT ROOT TEST RESULTS

The Augmented dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was used to test for the presence or absence of unit root in the data used for the empirical analysis. The test result is presented in the table below:

Table 2: Summary of Unit Root Results

VARIABLE	LEVEL		1ST DIFFERENCE		ORDER OF INTEGRATION	REMARKS
	ADF VALUE	5% CV	ADF VALUE	5% CV		
RGDP	-2.508949	-2.938987	-6.264535	-2.941145	I(1)	Stationary
ATM	-1.095317	-2.938987	-5.980892	-2.941145	I(1)	Stationary
POS	-0.333275	-2.938987	-8.029253	-2.941145	I(1)	Stationary
IB	0.639273	-2.943427	-6.120782	-2.941145	I(1)	Stationary
MB	-2.796935	-2.941145	-7.638829	-2.941145	I(1)	Stationary

Source: Student’s computation (see apendix)

The unit root test results in Table 2 above indicates that none of the variables (RGDP, ATM, POS, IB, and MB) is stationary at level. This is evident as their ADF values (2.508949, 1.095317, 0.333275, 0.639273 and 2.796935) were less than the 5% critical values (2.938987, 2.938987, 2.938987, 2.943427 and 2.941145), but they became stationary upon first differencing as their ADF values (6.264535, 5.980892, 8.029253, 6.120782 and 7.638829) became greater than the values of the 5% critical value (2.941145, 2.941145, 2.941145, 2.941145 and 2.941145). Since they all became stationary after the first differencing, we proceed to conduct cointegration test and short-run speed of adjustment from long-run disequilibrium

VII. JOHANSEN COINTEGRATION TEST RESULTS

The cointegration test seeks to ascertain whether or not a long-run relationship exists between the variables. The null hypothesis states that there is no cointegrating relation among the variables. With the Johansen cointegration test, we test that there is at least one cointegrating equation. Since there are five variables in the model, we then test to know if there are one or two or up to five cointegrating equations. Empirical results from the Johansen cointegrating analysis are presented in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Cointegration Result

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.919227	156.7331	69.81889	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.567080	61.12091	47.85613	0.0018
At most 2	0.422096	29.30726	29.79707	0.0569
At most 3	0.198337	8.470034	15.49471	0.4166
At most 4	0.001826	0.069468	3.841466	0.7921

Source: Student’s Computation (See appendix)

From table 3 above, the results of the cointegration indicated that the trace statistics is greater than the critical value at 5 percent level of significance in two of the equations. This shows that there is a cointegrating relationship among the variables used to model the relationship between Economic growth and Electronic banking in Nigeria for the period under study. The p-values (0.0000, and 0.0018) which are less than 0.05 significant value confirms that. Hence we reject the null hypothesis which states that there is no cointegrating relationship among the variables. The test result shows the existence of a long-run relationship in two cointegrating equations at 5% significance level.

VIII. VECTOR ERROR CORRECTION MODEL TEST RESULTS

VECM is conducted to check the speed of adjustment from short-run dynamics to their long-run static disposition

Table 4: VECM (Least Squares) Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ECM(-1)	-0.259649	0.113807	-2.281476	0.0313
D(RGD(-1))	0.028463	0.172926	0.164596	0.8706
D(RGD(-2))	0.058177	0.168807	0.344634	0.7333
D(ATM(-1))	0.248396	0.119226	2.083398	0.0476
D(ATM(-2))	-0.037923	0.127008	-0.298584	0.7677
D(IB(-1))	-0.106763	0.046634	-2.289394	0.0308
D(IB (-2))	0.007192	0.051718	0.139059	0.8905
D(MB(-1))	0.017082	0.082613	0.206774	0.8379
D(MB(-2))	0.158507	0.081634	1.941666	0.0635
D(POS(-1))	-0.062588	0.099215	-0.630833	0.5339
D(POS(-2))	-0.190947	0.088870	-2.148614	0.0415
C	0.012198	0.011287	1.080689	0.2902
R-squared	0.589745	Mean dependent var		0.019595
Adjusted R-squared	0.409233	S.D. dependent var		0.058343
S.E. of regression	0.044843	Akaike info criterion		-3.114675
Sum squared resid	0.050273	Schwarz criterion		-2.592215
Log likelihood	69.62148	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.930483
F-statistic	3.267067	Durbin-Watson stat		2.108610
Prob(F-statistic)	0.006853			

Source: Student’s computation (See Appendix)

Given the fact that there is presence of a cointegrating vector among the variables as shown by the cointegration tests, VECM is conducted to check the speed of adjustment from short-run dynamics to their long-run static disposition:

$$\Delta \text{RGDP}_{t-1} = -0.259649 \text{ECT}_{t-1} + 0.028463 \text{RGDP}_{t-1} + 0.058177 \text{RGDP}_{t-2} + 0.248396 \text{ATM}_{t-1} - 0.037923 \text{ATM}_{t-2} - 0.106763 \text{IB}_{t-1} = 0.007192 \text{IB}_{t-2} + 0.017082 \text{MB}_{t-1} + 0.158507 \text{MB}_{t-2} - 0.062588 \text{POS}_{t-1} - 0.190947 \text{POS}_{t-2} + 0.012198$$

From the table 4 above, ECM(-1) was consistent by assuming a negative value. This suggests that the ECM could correct any deviation from the long run equilibrium relationship between RGDP and the explanatory variables. The coefficient indicates a speedy adjustment of 26.964% per annum. This implies that following short-run disequilibrium, 25.964% of the adjustment to the long-run takes place within one year. The result in table 4.4 above shows that R² is 0.5897, which shows that the model explains about 58.97% of the total variations in Economic growth as explained by the independent variables during the period of the study, while 41.03% is explained by variables not included in the model.

The result also shows the F-statistics = 3.267067, which is used to test the model of the study to ascertain if there exist significant relationship between the parameters. The probability of the F-statistics value is 0.006853. This shows that a significant relationship exists between economic growth and electronic banking. This is evidenced by the probability value which is less than the 0.05 level of significance.

At 2.11; the Durbin-Watson statistics suggest absence of serial autocorrelation.

IX. GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST RESULTS

Table 5: Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
D(IB) does not Granger Cause D(ATM)	37	1.53399	0.2311
D(ATM) does not Granger Cause D(IB)		0.19023	0.8277
D(MB) does not Granger Cause D(ATM)	37	4.33563	0.0216
D(ATM) does not Granger Cause D(MB)		0.17612	0.8393
D(POS) does not Granger Cause D(ATM)	37	0.14527	0.8654
D(ATM) does not Granger Cause D(POS)		4.03275	0.0274
D(RGDP) does not Granger Cause D(ATM)	37	0.63321	0.5374
D(ATM) does not Granger Cause D(RGDP)		2.96052	0.0661
D(MB) does not Granger Cause D(IB)	37	15.4323	2.E-05
D(IB) does not Granger Cause D(MB)		0.12815	0.8802
D(POS) does not Granger Cause D(IB)	37	14.8387	3.E-05
D(IB) does not Granger Cause D(POS)		0.69142	0.5082
D(RGDP) does not Granger Cause D(IB)	37	0.66299	0.5222
D(IB) does not Granger Cause D(RGDP)		1.83027	0.1768
D(POS) does not Granger Cause D(MB)	37	6.65289	0.0038
D(MB) does not Granger Cause D(POS)		0.38859	0.6812

D(RGDP) does not Granger Cause D(MB)	37	0.29908	0.7435
D(MB) does not Granger Cause D(RGDP)		0.48952	0.6174
<hr/>			
D(RGDP) does not Granger Cause D(POS)	37	2.17048	0.1306
D(POS) does not Granger Cause D(RGDP)		0.76511	0.4736
<hr/>			

Source: Author’s computation using Eviews 8.

Here we are testing to ascertain the causality effect of the variables against themselves. This is to show if they affect each other in any way or not. As usual, the testing is done on 5% confidence interval. If the value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative, but if it is not, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude.

From the table below, we can see that IB and ATM does not Granger cause each other . We can also see that MB affects ATM while ATM does not affect MB in return. The result also shows that ATM granger causes POS while POS does not granger cause ATM. It can be deduced from the result that neither RGDP nor ATM granger causes each other. MB affects IB while IB does not affect MB, same way with POS and IB. It is clear that RGDP and IB, does not affect each other. From the table, we can see that POS affects MB while MB does not affect POS. It is very obvious that RGDP and MB does not affect each other, same way RGDP and POS has nothing to do against each other.

X. DISCUSSION OF MAJOR FINDINGS:

$$RGDP = 0.012198 + 0.248396ATM - 0.106763IB + 0.017082MB - 0.0625588POS$$

The equation above shows the estimated regression equation used to analyse the impact of Electronic Banking on Economic growth in Nigeria. The equation shows that ATMs and MB were found to have a positive impact on economic growth while POS and WB showed a negative impact. ATM, which has a statistical significance relationship with RGDP has a coefficient value of 0.248396. This implies that a unit change in ATM will increase Economic growth by 24.8396%, if other factors are kept constant. IB which also has a significant relationship with RGDP has a negative coefficient value of -0.106763. This implies that an inverse relationship exists between the variables. A unit increase or decrease in IB would lead to 10.68% decrease or increase in RGDP.

No significant relationship exists between POS, MB and RGDP. This could be as a result of many factors.

Nigerians are scared of making use of POS in their day to day transactions. This is because most times it takes longer time to reverse money wrongly debited from customer’s account during POS transactions. Sometimes the money is not reversed at all except with a persistent uproar from the customer, which makes him to spend more money in going to the bank branches or even money on airtime as he calls the bank’s customer service line to have his money reversed.

The charge on POS transactions is also a discouraging factor to the customers as the extra charges are unplanned expenses which eat into their income. When the income of customers keep being debited as bank charges, they can’t count them as money spent on consumables and thus the GDP is affected as the customers have less money to spend.

Another discouraging factor is that POS is easily used to perpetrate different forms of fraud. This is because it portable and very easy to navigate. It does not have second order security measures like internet banking that requires an OTP before a transaction can be completed.

The use of Mobile Banking has not been generally accepted by Nigerians as it comes with a whole lot of challenges too. It has an unfriendly user interface where customers who do not have clear knowledge of how to operate phones find it difficult to make transactions using mobile banking.

Because it uses mobile networks, the unstable network provided by network providers in Nigeria makes it unreliable as customers do not trust it to deliver at all times. This has led to its poor usage and thus led to its insignificant impact in the economic growth of Nigeria.

The R- square which was 58.97% and depicts goodness of fit as it shows that the explanatory could explain about 58.97% of the fluctuation in the inflation rate. ECM(-1) was consistent by assuming a negative value. This suggests that the ECM could correct any deviation from the long run equilibrium relationship between RGDP and the explanatory variables. The coefficient indicates a speedy adjustment of 26.964% per annum. The result of the study further showed that there is a long-run relationship between e-banking and economic growth and that e-banking Gsranger causes economic growth in Nigeria.

This is in agreement with the findings of Ogbeide, Nwamaka and Ishiuwu (2016) who investigated the impact of electronic banking on Nigerian economic growth.

XI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The result of the analysis shows that Electronic Banking has a significant relationship with Nigeria's economic growth, while Point of Sales, Internet Banking and Mobile Banking, individually have no significant effect on Nigeria's economic growth, while Automated Teller Machine has significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria for the period under consideration.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

The government should reduce the charges on the use of electronic means of transactions so as to encourage people to use them more often.

The government should improve the technological base of the country and engage in technological awareness in areas that have not experienced much technological effects. This is to make them see the need for the adoption of technology, and how it makes banking easier.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Anyanwu, M. (1999) Theory and Policy of Money and Banking, Enugu, Hossana publication Ayo, A.O. (1999). Emergence of Payment Systems in the era of e-commerce in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects. *Delta Business Education Journal*, 1 (6), 64-72.
- [2.] Babatunde, M.O. and Salawudeen, M.O. (2017). Analysis of the Impact of Electronic Banking on Customers' Satisfaction in Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Business and Management*, 7(3):030-042
- [3.] Babatunde, O. & Ogbeide, S (2017). E-Banking in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(6): 15 - 24.
- [4.] Delali, K. (2010). The Challenges of Implementing Electronic Payment System: The case of Ghana's E-zwich payment system MBA Thesis.
- [5.] Erhan, A. & Saudi, A. (2013). An overview of GDP and internet banking relations in the European Union versus China. *Procedia - Social Sciences and Behavioural Sciences*, 99(9):36 - 45
- [6.] Hassan, M. T., Mukhtar, A., Ullah, R. K., Shafique, H., and Rehman, S. U., (2012), Customer Service Quality Perception of Internet Banking, *International Journal of Learning & Development*, 2(2), 101-111.
- [7.] Isibor A.A, Omarkhanlen A.E., Okoye I.U., Achugamonu B.U., Adebayo M.E., Afolabi G.T., and Ayodeji O.E. (2018). Impact of Electronic Banking Technology on Customers' Satisfaction and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 9(12): 536 - 544 Madueme, I. S. (2010) Evaluation of the impact of information communication technology on banking efficiency using the transcendental logarithmic production function and CAMEL rating, *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, 2(1) 1-6.
- [8.] Jain, A. & Hundal, B.S. (2006) Barriers In Mobile Banking Adoption In India *The IUP Journal of Bank Management*, 2006, vol. V, issue 3, 64-73 (2006)
- [9.] Krishnamurthy, B. & Wills, C.E. (2006). Generating a Privacy Footprint on the Internet. In *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference of the World Wide Web*, ACM Press
- [10.] Madueme, I. S. (2010) Evaluation of the Impact of Information Communication Technology on Banking Efficiency Using the Transcendental Logarithmic Production Function and Camel Rating. *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, Vol.2(1), 2010, 1-6
- [11.] Maiyo (2013) The Effect Of Electronic Banking On Financial Performance Of Commercial Banks In Kenya, Thesis, College of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Nairobi, Kenya (2013)
- [12.] Musa, A.C., Kurfi, S. A, & Hassan, H.C. (2015) The Impact of Online Banking on the Performance of Nigerian Banking Sector *International Journal of Finance and Economics*. Vol. 3.(1) 2015
- [13.] Obademi, O. E and E. Adegboyega (2014). Banks and Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Re- Examination of the Financial Repression Hypothesis, *American Journal of Business and Management*, 3, (1) /2016
- [14.] Ogbeide, O., Nwamaka, E. and Ishiwu V. N. (2016). An empirical investigation into the impact of electronic banking on Nigerian Economic Growth. *The Journal of Economics and Social Studies*, 8(1): 108 -121.
- [15.] Okifo J. & Igbunu, R. (2015). Electronic Payment System in Nigeria: Its Economic Benefits and Challenges. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(16): 56 - 62.

- [16.] Okoro, E.G., and Kigho, P. E. (2013). The problems and prospects of E-Transaction (The Nigerian Perspective): *Journal of Research and international Business and Management: 3(1):10- 16.*
- [17.] Okoro A.S. (2014). Impact of Electronic Banking Instruments on the Intermediation Efficiency of the Nigerian Economy. *International Journal of Accounting Research, 1(6): 14 -21.*
- [18.] Omotayo, G. (2007) A Dictionary of Finance, West Bourne, England: West Bourne Business School.
- [19.] Raja, J., Velmurgan, Senthil M. and Seetharaman A. (2008). E-Payments: Problems and Prospects. Malaysia: Journal of Internat Banking and Commerce.
- [20.] Paul, L., (2006). the role of technology and scope of remote channels, their implication, strength, weakness, opportunities and threats in banking sector. *Information & Management Journal 40(3):191-204*
- [21.] Petkovski, M and J. Kjosevski (2014): Does Banking Sector Development Promote Economic growth? An Empirical Analysis for Selected Countries in Central and South Eastern Europe, *Economic Research, 27, (1): 55–66,*
- [22.] Raghavan, R.S. (2006). Perception of Indian Banks in 2020. The Chartered Accountant, October issue, 600-606.

APPENDIX

A1: Data Presentation in logged form

YEAR	LOGRGDP	LOGATM	LOGPOS	LOGIB	LOGMB
2009Q1	3.745966	2.138997	0.545307	0.641474	-1.22185
2009Q2	3.776504	2.163072	0.439333	0.715167	-0.95861
2009Q3	3.827255	2.100784	0.394452	1.718253	-0.284
2009Q4	3.843178	2.143608	0.359835	1.3485	-0.23657
2010Q1	4.106883	1.796505	0.44248	0.52763	-0.06048
2010Q2	4.118645	1.906981	0.426511	0.62941	0.136721
2010Q3	4.161865	2.06032	0.447158	0.997386	0.264818
2010Q4	4.176695	2.150756	0.651278	0.873902	0.409933
2011Q1	4.166907	2.523109	0.79796	1.382557	0.521138
2011Q2	4.182694	2.5619	0.80956	1.34262	0.570543
2011Q3	4.21402	2.588249	0.936514	0.803457	0.699838
2011Q4	4.241261	2.67768	0.984527	0.85187	0.840733
2012Q1	4.222068	2.657811	0.271842	0.804139	0.033424
2012Q2	4.254507	2.684163	0.941511	0.840733	0.692847
2012Q3	4.272661	2.698718	1.168792	0.877371	0.860937
2012Q4	4.283774	2.737916	1.355068	1.030195	1.261025
2013Q1	4.267692	2.786219	1.419625	1.05576	1.359456
2013Q2	4.304268	2.829362	1.49052	0.971276	1.461198
2013Q3	4.31605	2.862865	1.63488	1.089552	1.530456
2013Q4	4.335142	2.910283	1.782831	1.154728	1.756484
2014Q1	4.309245	2.894344	1.829046	1.220108	1.821841
2014Q2	4.341582	2.930623	1.846646	1.150449	1.87017
2014Q3	4.366102	3.011959	1.892095	1.27738	1.936966
2014Q4	4.390314	3.006701	1.983807	1.386856	2.077295
2015Q1	4.209617	2.972184	1.983671	1.357172	1.96199
2015Q2	4.220711	2.983369	2.019407	1.231724	2.001907

2015Q3	4.260274	3.004957	2.050844	1.350054	2.03866
2015Q4	4.272894	3.024642	2.130977	1.468052	2.149219
2016Q1	4.350935	3.02938	2.160619	1.500922	2.131105
2016Q2	4.375431	3.054801	2.214075	1.41946	2.226033
2016Q3	4.429284	3.095797	2.278639	1.487986	2.348422
2016Q4	4.470288	3.186631	2.415941	1.639785	2.362313
2017Q1	4.418779	3.176684	2.456336	1.668106	2.415958
2017Q2	4.435628	3.188712	2.510719	1.569257	2.470175
2017Q3	4.473575	3.192779	2.561757	1.658774	2.379052
2017Q4	4.500346	3.263056	2.638639	1.743118	2.486884
2018Q1	4.457624	3.195609	2.676447	1.783475	2.517354
2018Q2	4.490735	3.20498	2.735303	1.726401	2.613387
2018Q3	4.528673	3.201673	2.813187	1.839289	2.697299
2018Q4	4.552274	3.23476	2.853911	2.345433	2.773011

A2: ATM AT LEVEL

Null Hypothesis: ATM has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.095317	0.7081
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.610453	
5% level	-2.938987	
10% level	-2.607932	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(ATM)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/08/19 Time: 09:45
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q2 2018Q4
 Included observations: 39 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ATM(-1)	-0.040010	0.036528	-1.095317	0.2805
C	0.138480	0.101874	1.359323	0.1823

R-squared	0.031407	Mean dependent var	0.028096
Adjusted R-squared	0.005228	S.D. dependent var	0.093338
S.E. of regression	0.093094	Akaike info criterion	-1.860502
Sum squared resid	0.320657	Schwarz criterion	-1.775191
Log likelihood	38.27979	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.829893
F-statistic	1.199720	Durbin-Watson stat	1.977686
Prob(F-statistic)	0.280457		

A3: ATM AT FIRST DIFFERENCE

Null Hypothesis: D(ATM) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.980892	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.615588	
5% level	-2.941145	
10% level	-2.609066	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(ATM,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/07/19 Time: 22:18
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q3 2018Q4
 Included observations: 38 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(ATM(-1))	-0.996824	0.166668	-5.980892	0.0000
C	0.028114	0.016239	1.731222	0.0920

R-squared	0.498405	Mean dependent var	0.000237
Adjusted R-squared	0.484472	S.D. dependent var	0.133555
S.E. of regression	0.095893	Akaike info criterion	-1.799978
Sum squared resid	0.331035	Schwarz criterion	-1.713789
Log likelihood	36.19958	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.769312
F-statistic	35.77107	Durbin-Watson stat	1.978141
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001		

A4: IB AT LEVEL

Null Hypothesis: IB has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 2 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	0.639273	0.9890
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.621023	
5% level	-2.943427	
10% level	-2.610263	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(IB)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/08/19 Time: 09:48
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q4 2018Q4
 Included observations: 37 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IB(-1)	0.070092	0.109643	0.639273	0.5271
D(IB(-1))	-0.150131	0.131942	-1.137855	0.2634
D(IB(-2))	-0.549973	0.127785	-4.303897	0.0001
C	-0.050976	0.139121	-0.366413	0.7164
R-squared	0.379422	Mean dependent var		0.016951
Adjusted R-squared	0.323006	S.D. dependent var		0.234839
S.E. of regression	0.193224	Akaike info criterion		-0.348123
Sum squared resid	1.232077	Schwarz criterion		-0.173970
Log likelihood	10.44028	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.286726
F-statistic	6.725405	Durbin-Watson stat		1.548593
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001150			

A5: IB AT FIRST DIFFERENCE

Null Hypothesis: D(IB) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-6.120782	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.615588	
5% level	-2.941145	
10% level	-2.609066	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(IB,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/07/19 Time: 22:16
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q3 2018Q4
 Included observations: 38 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(IB(-1))	-1.058723	0.172972	-6.120782	0.0000
C	0.044753	0.046544	0.961517	0.3427

R-squared	0.509964	Mean dependent var	0.011380
Adjusted R-squared	0.496352	S.D. dependent var	0.401505
S.E. of regression	0.284941	Akaike info criterion	0.378124
Sum squared resid	2.922882	Schwarz criterion	0.464313
Log likelihood	-5.184358	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.408789
F-statistic	37.46397	Durbin-Watson stat	1.684147
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

A6: MB AT LEVEL

Null Hypothesis: MB has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.796935	0.0682
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.615588	
5% level	-2.941145	
10% level	-2.609066	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(MB)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/08/19 Time: 09:50
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q3 2018Q4
 Included observations: 38 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MB(-1)	-0.092017	0.032899	-2.796935	0.0083
D(MB(-1))	-0.309632	0.150332	-2.059654	0.0469
C	0.259360	0.060465	4.289419	0.0001

R-squared	0.226375	Mean dependent var	0.098200
Adjusted R-squared	0.182168	S.D. dependent var	0.216414
S.E. of regression	0.195712	Akaike info criterion	-0.348693
Sum squared resid	1.340605	Schwarz criterion	-0.219410
Log likelihood	9.625175	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.302695
F-statistic	5.120785	Durbin-Watson stat	1.878288
Prob(F-statistic)	0.011202		

A7: MB AT FIRST DIFFERENCE

Null Hypothesis: D(MB) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-7.638829	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.615588	
5% level	-2.941145	
10% level	-2.609066	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(MB,2)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 09/07/19 Time: 22:14
Sample (adjusted): 2009Q3 2018Q4
Included observations: 38 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(MB(-1))	-1.229517	0.160956	-7.638829	0.0000
C	0.121872	0.038400	3.173725	0.0031

R-squared	0.618449	Mean dependent var	-0.004935
Adjusted R-squared	0.607850	S.D. dependent var	0.340861
S.E. of regression	0.213453	Akaike info criterion	-0.199601
Sum squared resid	1.640243	Schwarz criterion	-0.113413
Log likelihood	5.792424	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.168936
F-statistic	58.35171	Durbin-Watson stat	1.869217
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

A8: POS AT LEVEL

Null Hypothesis: POS has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-0.333275	0.9105
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.610453	
5% level	-2.938987	
10% level	-2.607932	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(POS)

Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/08/19 Time: 09:51
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q2 2018Q4
 Included observations: 39 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
POS(-1)	-0.011575	0.034731	-0.333275	0.7408
C	0.077151	0.060724	1.270516	0.2118
R-squared	0.002993	Mean dependent var		0.059195
Adjusted R-squared	-0.023953	S.D. dependent var		0.172884
S.E. of regression	0.174942	Akaike info criterion		-0.598799
Sum squared resid	1.132380	Schwarz criterion		-0.513488
Log likelihood	13.67658	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.568190
F-statistic	0.111073	Durbin-Watson stat		2.495888
Prob(F-statistic)	0.740808			

A9: POS AT FIRST DIFFERENCE.

Null Hypothesis: D(POS) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-8.029253	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.615588	
5% level	-2.941145	
10% level	-2.609066	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(POS,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/07/19 Time: 22:20
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q3 2018Q4
 Included observations: 38 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(POS(-1))	-1.271067	0.158305	-8.029253	0.0000
C	0.079719	0.028949	2.753759	0.0092
R-squared	0.641680	Mean dependent var		0.003860
Adjusted R-squared	0.631727	S.D. dependent var		0.277964
S.E. of regression	0.168684	Akaike info criterion		-0.670386
Sum squared resid	1.024352	Schwarz criterion		-0.584197
Log likelihood	14.73732	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.639720

F-statistic	64.46891	Durbin-Watson stat	2.128887
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

A10: RGDP AT LEVEL

Null Hypothesis: RGDP has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.508949	0.1211
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.610453	
5% level	-2.938987	
10% level	-2.607932	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(RGDP)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/08/19 Time: 09:54
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q2 2018Q4
 Included observations: 39 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
RGDP(-1)	-0.112926	0.045009	-2.508949	0.0166
C	0.501683	0.191908	2.614187	0.0129

R-squared	0.145394	Mean dependent var	0.020675
Adjusted R-squared	0.122297	S.D. dependent var	0.057029
S.E. of regression	0.053428	Akaike info criterion	-2.971050
Sum squared resid	0.105618	Schwarz criterion	-2.885739
Log likelihood	59.93547	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.940441
F-statistic	6.294826	Durbin-Watson stat	2.180289
Prob(F-statistic)	0.016618		

A11: RGDP AT FIRST LEVEL

Null Hypothesis: D(RGDP) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-6.264535	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.615588	
5% level	-2.941145	
10% level	-2.609066	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(RGDP,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/07/19 Time: 22:22
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q3 2018Q4
 Included observations: 38 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(RGDP(-1))	-1.042750	0.166453	-6.264535	0.0000
C	0.021296	0.010092	2.110045	0.0419
R-squared	0.521559	Mean dependent var		-0.000183
Adjusted R-squared	0.508269	S.D. dependent var		0.083444
S.E. of regression	0.058514	Akaike info criterion		-2.787899
Sum squared resid	0.123261	Schwarz criterion		-2.701710
Log likelihood	54.97008	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.757234
F-statistic	39.24440	Durbin-Watson stat		1.994195
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

A12: COINTEGRATION RESULT

Date: 09/07/19 Time: 23:00
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q3 2018Q4
 Included observations: 38 after adjustments
 Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend
 Series: RGDP ATM IB MB POS
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.919227	156.7331	69.81889	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.567080	61.12091	47.85613	0.0018
At most 2	0.422096	29.30726	29.79707	0.0569
At most 3	0.198337	8.470034	15.49471	0.4166
At most 4	0.001826	0.069468	3.841466	0.7921

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
---------------------------	------------	---------------------	---------------------	---------

Effect of Electronic Banking on the Economic Growth of Nigeria [2009-2018]

None *	0.919227	95.61221	33.87687	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.567080	31.81365	27.58434	0.0134
At most 2	0.422096	20.83723	21.13162	0.0549
At most 3	0.198337	8.400566	14.26460	0.3394
At most 4	0.001826	0.069468	3.841466	0.7921

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by b'S11*b=I):

RGDP	ATM	IB	MB	POS
-1.752637	-0.513597	-3.471976	-4.488362	7.054010
-7.634713	2.143767	2.980630	-0.874360	-0.295615
3.711674	-4.411299	-0.730536	-0.782321	1.159400
8.064841	5.930922	0.401326	-2.711208	-1.307807
-12.39941	3.080303	-3.283195	3.486723	-2.707490

Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):

D(RGDP)	-0.001720	0.027327	-0.001643	-0.011442	-0.001081
D(ATM)	-0.003028	-0.043750	0.043088	-0.008250	-0.000345
D(IB)	0.209019	-0.115098	0.026689	-0.002695	-0.002183
D(MB)	0.080271	0.049491	0.059845	0.043163	-0.004562
D(POS)	-0.017005	0.015462	0.035520	0.035603	-0.004996

1 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood 203.1320

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

RGDP	ATM	IB	MB	POS
1.000000	0.293042	1.981001	2.560919	-4.024798
	(0.24922)	(0.16738)	(0.16997)	(0.23377)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(RGDP)	0.003014
	(0.01612)
D(ATM)	0.005306
	(0.02847)
D(IB)	-0.366335
	(0.05590)
D(MB)	-0.140686
	(0.05818)
D(POS)	0.029804
	(0.04825)

2 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood 219.0389

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

RGDP	ATM	IB	MB	POS
1.000000	0.000000	0.769985	1.311608	-1.949664

Effect of Electronic Banking on the Economic Growth of Nigeria [2009-2018]

0.000000	1.000000	(0.09952)	(0.10108)	(0.12937)
		4.132561	4.263241	-7.081341
		(0.34955)	(0.35506)	(0.45442)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(RGDP)	-0.205620	0.059466
	(0.06095)	(0.01715)
D(ATM)	0.339321	-0.092234
	(0.11139)	(0.03135)
D(IB)	0.512404	-0.354095
	(0.19025)	(0.05354)
D(MB)	-0.518535	0.064870
	(0.25054)	(0.07051)
D(POS)	-0.088245	0.041881
	(0.21455)	(0.06038)

3 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood 229.4575

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

RGDP	ATM	IB	MB	POS
1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.619752	-0.748421
			(0.13201)	(0.15425)
0.000000	1.000000	0.000000	0.550003	-0.634188
			(0.34094)	(0.39837)
0.000000	0.000000	1.000000	0.898532	-1.560087
			(0.12606)	(0.14729)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(RGDP)	-0.211719	0.066714	0.088623
	(0.06740)	(0.03835)	(0.03603)
D(ATM)	0.499250	-0.282308	-0.151367
	(0.10341)	(0.05883)	(0.05528)
D(IB)	0.611466	-0.471829	-1.088272
	(0.20639)	(0.11742)	(0.11033)
D(MB)	-0.296409	-0.199126	-0.174904
	(0.26111)	(0.14855)	(0.13959)
D(POS)	0.043595	-0.114810	0.079179
	(0.23089)	(0.13135)	(0.12343)

4 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood 233.6578

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

RGDP	ATM	IB	MB	POS
1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	-0.249891
				(0.03800)
0.000000	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	-0.191765
				(0.06663)
0.000000	0.000000	1.000000	0.000000	-0.837306
				(0.10556)
0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	1.000000	-0.804402
				(0.08780)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(RGDP)	-0.303999	-0.001149	0.084031	0.016133
	(0.08879)	(0.05784)	(0.03488)	(0.04030)
D(ATM)	0.432718	-0.331236	-0.154677	0.040500
	(0.14016)	(0.09131)	(0.05506)	(0.06361)

D(IB)	0.589732 (0.28184)	-0.487812 (0.18361)	-1.089353 (0.11072)	-0.851090 (0.12791)
D(MB)	0.051692 (0.34464)	0.056869 (0.22452)	-0.157582 (0.13539)	-0.567400 (0.15641)
D(POS)	0.330730 (0.30614)	0.096350 (0.19944)	0.093467 (0.12027)	-0.061511 (0.13894)

A13: VECTOR ERROR CORRECTION MODEL RESULTS

Vector Error Correction Estimates
 Date: 09/08/19 Time: 10:02
 Sample (adjusted): 2009Q4 2018Q4
 Included observations: 37 after adjustments
 Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

CointegratingEq:	CointEq1
RGDP(-1)	1.000000
ATM(-1)	-0.260689 (0.11015) [-2.36675]
IB(-1)	0.078960 (0.18877) [0.41830]
MB(-1)	0.412324 (0.21612) [1.90786]
POS(-1)	-0.589933 (0.32753) [-1.80113]
C	-3.314956

Error Correction:	D(RGDP)	D(ATM)	D(IB)	D(MB)	D(POS)
CointEq1	-0.259649 (0.11381) [-2.28148]	0.508108 (0.21310) [2.38434]	0.970002 (0.44567) [2.17648]	0.759431 (0.48375) [1.56989]	1.011679 (0.36756) [2.75241]
D(RGDP(-1))	0.028463 (0.17293) [0.16460]	-0.197469 (0.32380) [-0.60985]	0.498735 (0.67718) [0.73648]	0.707395 (0.73503) [0.96240]	0.368388 (0.55849) [0.65961]
D(RGDP(-2))	0.058177 (0.16881) [0.34463]	-0.047549 (0.31609) [-0.15043]	-0.340995 (0.66105) [-0.51583]	0.378626 (0.71753) [0.52768]	-0.033226 (0.54519) [-0.06094]
D(ATM(-1))	0.248396 (0.11923) [2.08340]	-0.248170 (0.22325) [-1.11163]	-0.593416 (0.46690) [-1.27098]	-0.887126 (0.50678) [-1.75051]	-0.765427 (0.38506) [-1.98780]

Effect of Electronic Banking on the Economic Growth of Nigeria [2009-2018]

D(ATM(-2))	-0.037923 (0.12701) [-0.29858]	0.146904 (0.23782) [0.61771]	-1.174847 (0.49737) [-2.36212]	-0.927205 (0.53986) [-1.71750]	-0.945295 (0.41020) [-2.30450]
D(IB(-1))	-0.106763 (0.04663) [-2.28939]	0.045793 (0.08732) [0.52442]	0.242702 (0.18262) [1.32900]	0.298324 (0.19822) [1.50501]	0.343531 (0.15061) [2.28090]
D(IB(-2))	0.007192 (0.05172) [0.13906]	-0.100033 (0.09684) [-1.03296]	-0.058936 (0.20253) [-0.29100]	0.555154 (0.21983) [2.52535]	0.591579 (0.16703) [3.54167]
D(MB(-1))	0.017082 (0.08261) [0.20677]	0.037975 (0.15469) [0.24549]	-0.525869 (0.32351) [-1.62549]	-0.502949 (0.35115) [-1.43229]	-0.497728 (0.26681) [-1.86546]
D(MB(-2))	0.158507 (0.08163) [1.94167]	-0.026904 (0.15286) [-0.17600]	-0.516941 (0.31968) [-1.61704]	-0.262078 (0.34699) [-0.75528]	-0.351151 (0.26365) [-1.33187]
D(POS(-1))	-0.062588 (0.09921) [-0.63083]	0.046819 (0.18578) [0.25202]	0.616802 (0.38853) [1.58753]	0.188743 (0.42172) [0.44756]	0.114203 (0.32043) [0.35640]
D(POS(-2))	-0.190947 (0.08887) [-2.14861]	0.056737 (0.16641) [0.34095]	0.649441 (0.34802) [1.86611]	0.258811 (0.37775) [0.68514]	0.166737 (0.28702) [0.58092]
C	0.012198 (0.01129) [1.08069]	0.032570 (0.02113) [1.54104]	0.086067 (0.04420) [1.94717]	0.136326 (0.04798) [2.84150]	0.148970 (0.03645) [4.08655]
R-squared	0.589745	0.453654	0.611680	0.347322	0.521413
Adj. R-squared	0.409233	0.213262	0.440819	0.060144	0.310834
Sum sq. resids	0.050273	0.176267	0.770959	0.908306	0.524392
S.E. equation	0.044843	0.083968	0.175609	0.190610	0.144830
F-statistic	3.267067	1.887144	3.579990	1.209429	2.476098
Log likelihood	69.62148	46.41277	19.11348	16.08048	26.24331
Akaike AIC	-3.114675	-1.860150	-0.384512	-0.220567	-0.769909
Schwarz SC	-2.592215	-1.337690	0.137947	0.301893	-0.247449
Mean dependent	0.019595	0.030648	0.016951	0.082622	0.066472
S.D. dependent	0.058343	0.094667	0.234839	0.196614	0.174460
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		1.11E-11			
Determinant resid covariance		1.56E-12			
Log likelihood		240.4068			
Akaike information criterion		-9.481448			
Schwarz criterion		-6.651457			